

Voice control home automation system

INTRODUCTION

Automation is becoming increasingly important in daily life and the global economy. Engineers try to construct complicated systems by combining automated equipment with mathematical and organizational tools for a continuously growing range of applications and human activities. As technology and intelligent services have developed, people's expectations and ideas about how services should be offered and accessed at home have changed significantly. This has enabled the transformation of the traditional home into a smart home; thus, the concept of home automation systems has evolved.

provides an effective GUI for providing this functionality. This system makes use of 8051

microcontroller. The Bluetooth receiver is interfaced with microcontroller in order to accept the commands and then react accordingly. It operates the loads through a set of relays using a relay driver IC. Relays are used between loads and the control unit.

[1]. Thus, this is particularly most reliable for people with disabilities, because they cannot use ordinary electrical switches due to discomfort in movement, they must continue to rely on their family members or caregivers to perform these obligations. Recent years have seen

much research focused on producing assistive technologies to get over this restriction of differently-abled persons in controlling their living environment

[2]. These persons can converse adequately despite not executing the necessary limb movements to control the switches. Therefore, the effort has centered on developing voice based control systems to replace the physical actions essential for switching operations

[3]. Communication technology has improved substantially over the past few decades, making it practical and economical for an individual to own a mobile phone. Numerous Android-compatible apps are available on Google Play Store.

1. RELATED WORK

All the related works that have been done by other researchers that are related to the current research problem are summarized in this section.

- Voice control of home appliances using Android.
- Design of an Intelligent Voice Controlled Home Automation system.
- Home Appliances Control using Android App. .

This paper presents the development of home appliances based on voice

command using Android. This system has been designed to assist and provide the support to elderly and disabled people at home. Google application has been used as voice recognition and process the voice input from the smartphone. In this paper, the voice input has been captured by the android and will be sent to the Arduino Uno. Bluetooth module in Arduino Uno received the signal and processed the input signal to control the light and fan. The proposed system intended to control electrical appliances with relatively user-friendly interface and ease of installation. We have demonstrated up to 20 meter of range to control the home appliances via Bluetooth.

2.2.Design of an Intelligent Voice Controlled Home Automation System.

With the development of modern technology, smart phones have become a necessity for every person on this planet. Applications are being developed on Android systems that are useful to us in various ways. Another upcoming technology is natural language processing which enables us to command and control things with our voice. Combining all of these, our paper presents a micro controller based voice controlled home automation system using smart phones. Such a system will enable

users to have control over every appliance in his/her home with their voice. All that the user needs is an Android smart phone, which is present in almost everybody's hand nowadays, and a control circuit. The control circuit consists of an Arduino Uno microcontroller, which processes the user commands and controls the switching of devices. The connection between the microcontroller and the smart phone is established via Bluetooth, a widespread wireless technology used for sharing data.

2. PROJECT SCOPE

By using voice commands, a user shall be able to switch on and off home devices such as lights, fan, multimedia etc. A key feature of this system is its flexibility to adapt to different scenarios and devices, as the user is able to add, delete and edit rooms, user accounts and devices. For security purposes, the system requires login to access it and there are two kinds of users: the admin user and the common user. From a technical point of view, the system utilizes a local network in which the UI and the Arduino have different roles.

Arduino UNO

Arduino is an open source computer hardware and software company, project, and user community that designs and manufactures single-

board microcontrollers and microcontroller kits for building digital devices and interactive objects that can sense and control objects in the physical and digital world. Board designs use a variety of microprocessors and controllers. The boards are equipped with sets of digital and analog input/output (I/O) pins.

Bluetooth Module HC-05

HC-05 module is an easy to use Bluetooth SPP (Serial Port Protocol) module, designed for transparent wireless serial connection setup. The HC-05 Bluetooth Module can be used in a Master or Slave configuration, making it a great solution for wireless communication. This serial port Bluetooth module is fully qualified Bluetooth V2.0+EDR (Enhanced Data Rate) 3Mbps Modulation with complete 2.4GHz radio transceiver and baseband. It uses CSR Blue core 04-External single chip Bluetooth system with CMOS technology and with AFH (Adaptive Frequency Hopping Feature).

Microcontroller

Microphone and Voice Recognition Module The microphone used to get voice commands to the voice recognition module is a simple collar type microphone with 3.5 mm jack. Elec house voice recognition module v3 is used for the voice recognition process. The voice recognition module needs to be trained before it can be put to actually recognize the voice commands. The speech input from the microphone is given to the voice recognition module and there the input speech is compared with the previously trained voice commands and if there is a match then control action through control circuit is taken.

Relays

The mechanical relay has capability for acting as switch for turning on and off electrical loads. They work simply by providing small electrical power in form of electrical signal. This allows high power loads controlled by using small amount of power. The mechanical relay uses electromechanical coil to open and

close the circuit. When small amount of current passes through coil it excites the coil and generates magnetic field and either pull the bar or release the bar which is used for opening and closing the circuit, here opening and closing means restricts flow of current and vice versa respectively. (Refer Figure 7) a relay is an electromagnetic switch. In other words it is activated when a current is applied to it. Normally a relay is used in a circuit as a type of switch (as shown below). There are different types of relays and they operate at different voltages. When a circuit is built the voltage that will trigger it has to be considered. In this project the relay circuit is used to turn the appliances on/off. The high/low signal is supplied from the Arduino Uno microcontroller. When a low voltage is given to the relay of an appliance it is turned off and when a high voltage is given it is turned on. The relay circuit to drive four appliances in the Voice-operated Android and Arduino Home automation system is shown below. The number of appliances can be modified according to the user's requirements.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM MODEL

The system is designed by using three main components, first is microcontroller Arduino Uno, second is Bluetooth module HC-05 and third is mechanical relay. Firstly user gives the command to microcontroller by using speech recognition system of smartphone and system software application via Bluetooth module HC-05. The microcontroller acts accordingly to the command give user and controls the functionality of mechanical relay. The Arduino Uno is programmed using Arduino IDE which is software; the user interface application is Arduino Voice Control. As the figure 8 shows it is the home automation system or we called Voice Controlled Home Automation.

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND TEST PROTOTYPE

A low cost and efficient smart home system is presented in the proposed design shown in Fig.8. This system has two main modules: the hardware interface module and the software communication module. At the heart of this system is the Arduino Mega 2560 microcontroller which is also capable of functioning as a micro web server and the interface for all the hardware modules. All communication and controls in this system pass through the microcontroller. Using the above mentioned components we implement our system on a breadboard. The microcontroller device with the Bluetooth module and relay circuit needs to be attached with the switch board. Then we need to launch the android based application-“ARDUINO VOICE CONTROL” on our Smartphone. Through the application we can instruct the microcontroller to switch on/off an appliance. After getting the instruction through the Bluetooth module the microcontroller gives the signal to the relay board. The application first searches for the Bluetooth device. If it is available then it launches the voice recognizer. It reads the voice and converts the audio signal into a string. It produces a value for each appliance

which will be given to the microcontroller device. The microcontroller uses the port in serial mode. After reading the data it decodes the input value and sends a signal to the parallel port through which the relay circuit will be activated. In this work we use Bluetooth module. We can also attach a GSM module to do the work, using which the application can be used anywhere where a mobile network is available.

5.FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

Arduino based device control using Bluetooth on Smartphone project can be enhanced to control the speed of the fan or volume of the buzzer etc. Home automation and Device controlling can be done using Internet of Things technology. Replacement of Bluetooth by GSM modem may achieve device controlling by sending SMS using GSM modem.

6.CONCLUSIONS

The prototype of the voice controlled home automation system is fabricated in laboratory. The test results of experimental prototype has proven to work satisfactorily by connecting sample appliances to it and the appliances were successfully controlled from a wireless mobile device. Also the Bluetooth client was

successfully tested on a multitude of different mobile phones from different manufacturers, thus proving its portability and wide compatibility. Thus a low-cost home automation system was successfully designed, implemented and tested. The project has been designed by keeping in mind needs of all consumers for performing operation of turning on and off electrical appliance by using user interface device by giving voice commands wirelessly. The Bluetooth module can be removed and instead of Bluetooth module high range communication device can be implemented in system for better and reliable use of system.

9. REFERENCES

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